

PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF NON-STEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS WITH GASTROPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES

Kurbonov Asilbek

Student of the Faculty of Treatment Tashkent Medical Academy
Department of Clinical Pharmacology, Tashkent Medical Academy
Scientific Supervisor-Senior Lecturer **Aripdjanova Sh.S.**

Introduction. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs are one of the most widely used groups of drugs. The world medical literature contains a huge amount of data on the side effects of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug, primarily on "Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs -gastropathy". A promising drug from the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs group is amtolmetin guacil, which has an efficacy comparable to traditional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and a good safety profile for the cardiovascular system and gastrointestinal tract.

The aim of this study. The effectiveness and tolerability of Nayzilat in reducing pain sensitivity and its tolerability, adverse effects on the gastrointestinal tract, and the development of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs-gastropathy.

Materials and methods. The study included 20 patients with a diagnosis of gonarthrosis (10) and (10) arthrosis of the hip joint grade II/III with their consent. The diagnosis was verified after a comprehensive clinical, instrumental (X-ray, computed tomography) examination without severe concomitant diseases and patients with a history of gastric and duodenal ulcer. All patients were prescribed Nayzilat at a dose of 600 mg/day in tablet form 2 times a day. The duration of treatment ranged from 10 days to 4 weeks. No additional antisecretory or gastroprotective drugs were prescribed. During the treatment, the dynamics of the following parameters were assessed: the severity of pain syndrome using a visual analog scale questionnaire to assess pain sensitivity (up to 4 cm - weak, 4-7 cm moderate and 7-10 cm strong) on the 5th, 10th day and at the 4th week of therapy and blood tests to determine the level of inflammatory markers C-reactive protein before and during the 2nd week of therapy, and the condition of the gastrointestinal tract was assessed based on the patient's subjective sensations, such as abdominal pain, heartburn, and an endoscopic examination was performed before and after 4 weeks of using the drug.

Research results. Before the therapy, all patients had severe pain in the joints during movement, an average of 5-8 cm (6.5 cm according to visual analog scale), and morning stiffness. Pain at rest was noted by 16 (80%) of the examined patients. Severe impairment of the function of the affected joints was noted in 14 (70%) patients. All study participants had synovitis.

Pain relief was achieved in 5 (25%) patients on the 5th day, in 16 (80%) on the 10th day, in 18 (90%) on the 4th week of therapy, in 2 (5%) patients mild pain in the joints during movement persisted. The pain index by the end of the week averaged 4 cm, which corresponds to low intensity, which is significantly lower than the indicators before treatment. During 4 weeks of using the drug, 18 patients did not complain of heartburn, dyspeptic disorders and pain in the epigastrium; 2 patients had complaints from the gastrointestinal tract at various stages of treatment in the form of heartburn and discomfort in the epigastrium, and additional administration of Proton-pump inhibitors was required. The course therapy with the inclusion of the Nayzilat, along with the relief of pain syndrome, was accompanied by the normalization of the emotional state, restoration of night sleep. This led to an increase in the quality of life of patients.

Conclusions. Amtolmetin guacil has pronounced analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects, and given its unique mechanism of stomach protection, it allows the drug to be

prescribed without additional gastroprotective drugs for long courses without the development of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs gastropathy, which is economically advantageous.